

Bibliography of Uyghur language articles on literature from the journal *Bulaq*.

Compiled by Nathan Light, 1996.

Updated and published in this version with DOI at Zenodo.org in 2022.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5821941

RIGHTS: Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0) <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

***Bulaq: Uyghur kilassik edibiyati mejmu'esi*. Published in Ürümchi, China.**

A slightly annotated index to articles from the first 12 years of the Uyghur literary journal *Bulaq* (1980-1992) as a finding aid for scholarly resources in Uyghur. This journal was the main venue for discussing and publishing editions of Uyghur manuscript works, discussing the history of Uyghur literature, translating foreign language literary and academic works, and giving biographies of authors. Many of the poets that are now included in the Uyghur canon had their first print publication in this journal. It also includes many works and analyses of oral traditional material.

I posted this online from 1996-2005 on my old website at University of Toledo. I published this bibliography partly to fulfill a promise I made in 1993 to Mähämmättursun Bahavidin, the editor of *Bulaq*, when he graciously let me acquire a complete run of this journal up to 1992. Now most volumes of *Bulaq* have been scanned and can now be downloaded at <https://turkistanilibrary.com> using the search term بۇلاق .

Issue #1 (1, 1980)

[first two pages consist of a note from Isma'il Ämat, reproduced in manuscript, dated June 9, 1980.]

Mentimin Yusup. "Kilassik Ädibiyat tetqiqatiniñ yäñi baharini qizghin kutuvalayli," pp. 1-8.

Imin Tursun. "Ädibiy miras häm väsiqilirimiz," pp. 9-75. [begins "Uyghurs are one of the peoples with the longest cultural and artistic histories. And they are considered to be the oldest of the Turkic speakers."]

Abdushukur Turdi. "Zälili vä uniñ Säpärnamäsi," pp. 76-113. [excerpts with glosses are included (87-113)].

Abdirishit Islam. "Gherbi (Turdush Akhun) vä uniñ äsiri Kitap gherip," pp. 114-142. [on his work and life: lived 1802-1862 in Qashqar (114-121); excerpts from his work, consisting of 172 misra of 1756 total (121-142). They concern the topic of craftsmanship, agriculture, animals,

metal smithing. Giläm, l.13; much on the joys and sorrows of dihqançiliq (127-129); on fruit, food and God and halal and haram (130-133); gold, iron, silver (138-140); wood and gold? (141-142). Mäntions muqam ('place') l. 149, saz l. 159. and nava l. 58, but only to express other ideas.]

Abdurehim Otkur. "Muhakimätul lughätäyindin parçilär," pp. 143-161. [Nava'i's famous work - commentary with many quotes. Cites Belin's 1861 article translated by Näjip Asim, and the Turkish translation of 1897 of Nava'i's work.]

Turdi Samsaq. "Äkhmätsha Qariqash vä uniñ mäshhur mukhämmisi," pp. 162-173. [first published in Ghulja's Ittipaq journal in 1948. Salamnamä given here (167-173).]

Ibrahim Muti'i. "Irq putuk," pp. 174-185. [brief disussion of this Runic Turkic text, and a translation of its 103 lines (176-185).]

Turghun Almas. "Äpsanä vä rivayät," pp. 186-204. [discusses the concept of totem and the wolf totem of the Turks - cites a fairly long story from Abulghazi Shäjärä'i Turk about being saved from difficulty by a wolf. And the Northern Zhou in 6th c. in a qissä about the Turks, who are stated to be clearly a different tribe from the Huns, tells a story about a boy and a wolf. The wolf went to the south mountains and had 10 sons. Went to Altay and did iron smithing??. Cites another äpsanä. Then discusses the rivayät of Boko Khan. At the end summarizes saying that these two folk forms through romantism heavily influence the literature of later periods.]

"Rak Muqamigha sälinghan kilassik shäirlardin tallanmilar." Näshrge täyyarlighuçi:Ablimit Rozi. Pp. 205-212. [From Nava'i's Khaza'i'olma'ani - Ghara'ibossighar the first mätlä (205-207); Lutfi's Divan, page 9 (207-209); from Mäshräp and Huväyda (209-211); Zälili (211-212). Each poem has a translation on the following page, making it very difficult to follow. These do not match the Qorban Barat edition, except for the three misra beginning 'bagh içrä ...' that appear in the kiçik säliqä.]

Ghojähmet Yunus. Uyghur khälq mäsälliri toghrisida," pp. 213-221.

Mäkhmut Zäyidi. "Molla Zäyidin gäpçi," pp. 222-241. [Born in Baghra yeza of Lukçun in 1815, son of a well-known qoghunçi. He became a Molla and the Qazi restricted his gepçilik and qoshaq writing. Died sometime after 1880. Humorous stories of his life (225-241).]

"Ata väsiyiti (çočäk)". Teller: Qasim Qorban; editor: Sadir Sayim. Pp. 242-255.

Shayakhmät Qorban. "Ili khälq toy qoshaqliri," pp. 256-267. [six songs]

Mir Sultan. "Lopnur khälq qoshaqliri," pp. 268-306. [brief discussion of the poetic and linguistic features, and then a large collection of short and long songs.]

"Khälq maqal-tämsilliri." Äkhmät Hasim, rätlighuçi, pp. 307-310.

"Uyghur kilassik ädibiyatiniñ katlogi." tuzguçi: Haji Nurhaji. pp. 311-357. [introductory note says the author only includes Uyghur authors. The contents are as follows:

- "Alip Ärtoña" dastani, now only preserved as fragments in other divans.
- Altun Yaroq. Publ'd by Malov and Radlov, the ms. in Berlin.
- Asarä Imamiyä (Kälilä-Däminä). by Bidpayi Hikim, translated in 1131 A. H.
- Parčä sheirlar of Niyazi.
- Pändnamä. Isma'il Bek (Bi Nishan), written 1258 A.H., 10,948 misra.
- Pärhat-Sherin, Läyli-Mäjnun. Omär Baqi, written 1792.
- Tarikhiy Rāshidi.
- Tarikhiy Musqyun. Gives author and says written 110 years ago, 16 pages with a poem of Nava'i attached. Gives good information about Amannisa Khenim. Kept at the XASS.
- Tarikhiy Vätän Vaq'ati Khotän. Muhämmät Abdulla Haji. Poetic history of the city both before and after Islam, and including the resistance against the Qing. At XASS.
- Tarikhiy äsar vaq'ä Kashighr. Imir Hosuyin. Fairly complete description of contents, including history of Turks, of Islam coming to Qashqar, of Appaq Khoja and the White and Black mountain factions. The foreign consulates, and many figures of the 19th c. Also the child's game dum-dum-läväy-läväy. 280 pages. Kept at XASS.
- Tāzkirä Äzizan. 1771. 352 pp. Xj. Museum.
- Divan Ärshi. 116 pp.
- Durrilinjat. Abdurihim Nizari. 1889. 152 pp. Xj. Museum.
- Divan Emri. Poet died 1822.
- Divan Zälili. 336 pp.
- Divan Sadayi. Mir Häsän. Lithographed in Tashkent. 96 pp.
- Divan Nobiti. (two nuskhā described).
- DLT. MLK. No mention of any copies in Xj.
- Divan Zuhuri. 70 pp. [this is what is missing from my copy of Bulaq #9.]
- Ätibätul Häayiq. Not in Xj.
- Ärziyät. Molla Tokhti. From Aqsu of Chun Wang's time. 50 pp.
- Näphatil Unis. 1915 printing in Tashkent.
- Ishtiyaqnamä.
- Ghärbiy.
- Nava'i.
- Ärsilakhan Tāzkirisi. Molla Äyt. About Siyit Ärsilakhan's life; also the work Saqinamä included at the end. At the Xj. Science Academy.
- Jähdil Muqil. Quдрätilla bini Muhämmät Oshur (of Khotän). 1354 A.H.
- Čahar Divan. 2 copies.
- Čashtani Ilig Bäg. Pub'd in Japan as the 26th volume of a Buddhist collection.
- Čahar Därvish. Ämir Khusrav Dehlävi originally a Turkistanliq. Collection of stories in the style of the 1001 nights. Translated by Yaqup Khoja Pasha Khoja oghli, and printed in Tashkent 1324.
- Čañmuza Yusupkhan. Molla Bilal.
- Khämsä Nava'i.
- Kharabati.
- Khatirä Ghärbiy.
- Häyrätul'ābrar.
- Huväyda. Together with the history of Äjät Hisav, printed in Tashkent, 230 pp.

- Oghüznamä. Not in Xinjiang.
- Siya Rolmokhisin. Shämshidin ili Abdulla Yiñsari. Written 1863. On the followers of Appaq Khoja and the movements.
- Sadir Palvan.
- Shahnamä. Translated 1121 A.H. by Molla Khamush Akhun in Yärkän. 428 pp. at XASS.
- Rabi'ä Sä'idi. Abdurihim Nizari.
- Zupärnamä Shah Bahadır Khan. Molla Abdughappar. 1853 in Yäkän. About the decendants of Turpan Wang who ruled in Yäkän. All in Aruz form.
- Zopärnamä. Molla Shakir. Uč Turpan. On events of 1863 in Kučar.
- Zobdätul mäsa'il. Muhämmät Sadiq Kasghri. 1260 AH.
- Zopärnamä. Moghänini. Historical dastan.
- Farabi. "Ulugh Turk (Uyghur) päylasopi... . In Turki there are 20 or so works, and as for us, one or so are saqlanghan.
- Qissä'i Rabghuzi. Mentions none in Xinjiang.
- Qissä Ibrahim Ädhäm. Written in third c. AH. by Balkhliq. Printed 1335 AH. in Tashkent using Uyghur language.
- Yusup Khas Hajip. "Foji" copy at XASS.
- Kullyat Fuzuli.
- Kitabi Gherip. Turdush Akhun Katip.
- Yusup Äkhmät. Five nuskha.
- Yusup-Ziläykha. Molla Yunus Yärkändi.
- Tarkhiy Shäjrä'i Turk. Obulghazi Bahadırkhan. French translation 1726, this nuskha from Qazan. 22 pp.?
- Tarikhiy Ämynä.
- Ghäzälyart. Molla Bilal.
- Ghazat därmulik Čen. Molla Bilal. Printed at Qazan.
- Gherip-Sänäm. Muhämmät Yusup in 1343 AH. copied down this folk dastan at Khotän. 100 pp.
- Gulzar Binish. The Yeñisar poet Naqish (Savirakhun Khatip) translated from Säyikh [sic]
- Ghinaytulla (d. 1677)'s Bahar Ranish.
- Lutpi. Great Uyghur poet of the 15th century.
- No title. Mirza Mähmut Jaras. Lacking the beginning and end. About Korkhan-Koshluq. Chingiz and Chaghatay and their descendants. Abdurishit Khan and on the editing of the 12 Muqams.
- Mehzonilvahizin. Noruzkhan Katish. A täsävvup dastan by this Qäshqärliq. Written 1259 A.H. Contents: all sorts of political, scientific, and religious tänbih. 200 pages.
- Muhäbbätnamä - Mehnätkamä. Muhämmät Imin Hojam Quli Oghli Khrqti. Author died 1724. Wrote this poem while a gardener for Appaq Khoja in 1670. 198 pages.
- Mäshhunolha Qayiq. Mävlana Lutfi. Died 1465. Muhämmä Hosuyinbäg Oghli Taji Muhämmätbäg copied in 1812, called it Däkhöluljan änva - bulbul. "Originally" 514 pages.
- Märsiyä Gherip. The author, Gherip, is from Khotän.
- Muhäbbät Dastanliri. Abdurihim Nizari. Wrote from 1834-1838 when Turpan Wang came from Qäshqär to Turpan. Contains seven dastans all in same aruz väzn like that of Nava'i's Khämsä. 387 pages, 24000 misra.

- Mähbobilqulup. Nava'i. Copied in 1210 A.H. by Tokhti Mulla Yoldash Oghli. 60 pages.
- Nozugum. Molla Bilal binni Molla Yusup. Written 1882. On the brave Uyghur girl who resisted the Junghar in the 18th century.
- Navayiniñ Adalätpärvär toghrisida. Emir Hosuyin Sabori. A treatise on Nava'i's point of view as found in Säddi Iskändäri.
- Noruznamä. Shatorsha binni Akhun. Written in 1354 A.H. Poetry about the celebration of the "farmers'" New Year by the poet and students.
- Näsri Mirz Muhämmät Hosuyinbäg. Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. A reworking of Nava'i's Khämsä into prose in 1228 A.H. for the Yärkän Hakim, whose name the work bears. Description cites five dastans included, and says in the place of Sä'ibi Säyyarä is put the Muntiquttäyr. 862 pages.

"Kičik Lughät", pp. 357-360.

"Näshriyattin" pp. 361-362.

Issue #2 (2, 1980)

Abdurihim Nizari. "Mäs'od vä Dil'ara" pp. 6-135.

M. Khudabärdi. "Molla Muhämmät Niyazi," pp. 135-143.

Molla Mähämmät Niyazi. "Dastani Mänsur." pp. 144-218.

"Zäpärnämä dastani toghrisida" pp. 219-220.

Molla Shakir. "Zäpärnämä (dastan)." pp. 221-333.

A. Khoja, I. Yusup. "Altun Yaruq toghrisida" pp. 334-341.

"Altun Yaruq tin parčä" pp. 342-358.

"Altun Yaruq tin parčä" niñ tärjimisi. pp. 359-372.

Oghuz Namä. pp. 373-395.

Turghun Almas. Oghuz Namä.... pp. 396-420.

Imin Tursun. "Komulup Qalghan gohärlirimizni qazayli." pp. 421-427.

"Khälq äghiz ädibiyati," pp. 428-429.

"Sadir Palvan qoshaqliri," pp. 430-442.

"Khälq qiziqçisi Hisamidin çakhçaqliridin," pp. 444-458.

"Täm - Tutäm Shaldambay (čoçäk)" pp. 459-477.

Sali Khudabärdi. "Tepishmaqlar häqqidä" pp. 477-485.

"Khälq maqalliridin" pp. 486-489.

"Niyä khälq maqalliridin," p. 490.

Issue #3 (1, 1981)

Mähämmät Imin. "(about Mahmud Kashghari's DLT)." pp. 1-34.

Lutpi. "Gul vä nävroz," pp. 35-129.

"Qäländär Güzälliridin," pp. 130-184.

Mähzun Khotäni. "Divani Mähzun," pp. 185-207.

Molla Bilal binni Molla Yusup. "Nuzugum" pp. 208-225.

Khevir Tomur. "Abdiqadir Damolla (tarikhiy oçerik)" pp. 226-270.

Nim Shehit. "Miñ oy vä Pärhad - Shirin," pp. 270-346.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Sänobär (khälq dastani)" pp. 347-389.

"Qumul qoshaqliridin tallanma," pp. 390-437.

"Khasiyätlik ängushtär (čoçäk)" pp. 438-453.

"Väli Bapka (čoçäk)" pp. 454-465.

"Uyghur ädibiyati tarikhiniñ tätqiqat temiliri," pp. 466-485.

Issue #4 (2, 1981)

"Idiqut Padishalighi dövridiki sheirlardin nāmūnilär," pp. 1-37.

"Čashtani Ilik Bäk tin parčä," pp. 38-57.

"Säkkaki ghäzälliridin tallanma," pp. 58-103.

"Mäshräp Sheirliridin tallanma," pp. 104-151.

"Mähzun vä Gulnisa (dastan)" pp. 152-262.

Molla Bilal binni Mulla Yusup. "Čaņmoza Yusupkhan" pp. 263-280.

"Kolliyat Mäsnivi Kharabati din tallanmilar," pp. 280-306.

"Ismayil Haji vä uniņ sheirliri," pp. 307-314.

"Rävzätıl Zohradin parčä" pp. 314-328.

Häbibulla Eli Helim Haji Oghli. "Uyghur sha'iri Siyit Muhämmät vä uniņ Särhi Shikästä namliq äsiri häqqidä," pp. 329-340.

"Abdukhalıq Uyghur sheirliridin tallanmilar," pp. 341-402.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

Ärshidin Tatliq. "Uyghur khälq eghiz ädibiyati vä uniņ tarikhi häqqidä" pp. 403-441.

"Adil Padisha (čočäk)," pp. 442-461.

"Uyghur khälq qoshaqliridin," pp. 462-478.

Issue #5 (3, 1981)

"Gumnam ghäzälliri" pp. 1-128.

Molla Äläm Shähyari. "Gul vä bulbul" pp. 129-218.

Abdirihim Sabit. "Sha'irä Zibunnisa" pp. 219-227.

Mirähmät Siyit. "Sha'ir Tävpıq" pp. 228-253.

"Ähmäd Yunäkinıñ Hibätulhäqayıq dastanı" pp. 254-285.

Abdirihim Sabit. "Qaraghoja Khandanlıghı dävrıdiki Uyghur ädibiyatı toghrisıda," pp. 286- 312.

Haji Äkhmät. "Uyghur ädibiyatıda piroza žanırinıñ shäkillinishi vä ravajlinishi," pp. 313-332.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Mälikä Golroz (qissä)," pp. 333-360.

"Uyghur khälq maqal-tämsilliridin." pp. 361-387.

Issue #6 (1, 1982)

"Lutpi ghäzälliridin," pp. 1-45.

"Atayı ghäzälliridin," pp. 46-112.

Ähmıdi. "Sazlar munazirisi," pp. 113-128.

"Divanı Mähzun," pp. 129-145.

A. Nizari. "Läyli Mäjnun." pp. 146-265.

"Kulliyat Mäsnivi Kharabatı din tallanmılar," pp. 266-283.

Abdirihim Sabit. "Uyghur khälqniñ qadımçı mädinıyiti toghrisıda," pp. 284-309.

Haji Äkhmät. "Zohoridin Hakim Bäg dävrıdä Qäshqär rayonidiki mädinı hayat vä ädibiyat," pp. 310-339.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Shäkärıstan (dastan)," pp. 340-361.

Issue #7 (2, 1982)

Navayi. "Mäntiquttäyir," pp. 1-64.

"Fuzuli ghäzälliridin tallanma," pp. 65-100.

A. Nizari. "Rabi'ä - Sä'din" pp. 101-152.

"Divani Mähzun," pp. 153-183.

Khislät. "Mushuk bilän saçqan," pp. 184-202.

"Divani Sadayi din tallanma" pp. 203-282.

Dilbär Durghä. "Mäzlummar Ahi," pp. 283-289.

Qahar Barat. "Uyghur - Yänsäy yezighidiki Mängu tash yadikarliqliri vä bashqa yazma yadikarliqlar," pp. 290-313.

Abdukirim Rakhman. "Mädiniyät dunyasiniñ olmäs khatiriliri," pp. 314-328.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Boz Yigit, (dastan)" pp. 329-374.

"Dästurkhandiki Majra," pp. 375-379.

"Uyghur khälq maqal-tämsilliridin." pp. 380-385.

Issue #8 (3, 1982)

Navayi. "Mäntiquttäyir," pp. 1-136.

"Vamuq - Ozra (dastan)," pp. 137-164.

"Divan Nobiti," pp. 165-247.

"Divan Qari din tallanma" pp. 248-356.

"Divan Naqis" pp. 357-441.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Bulbul Goya (khälq dastani)" pp. 442-489.

Issue #9 (1983)

Navayi. "Mäntiquttäyir (davami)," pp. 1-91.

Ayazbik Qushçi. "Jahannamä." pp. 92-148.

Molla Bilal "Ghözäliyat," pp. 149-209.

"Divan Khästä din parçilar" pp. 210-230.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Ikki Dastan," pp. 231-237.

"Shahzade Pärrokh," pp. 238-283.

"Uyghur khälq maqal-tämsilliridin." pp. 284-286.

Issue #10 (1983)

"Uyghur Mani Sheirliri," pp. 1-35.

A. Nizari. "Bähram - Dilaram" pp. 36-113.

Khislät. "Hädiyä'i Khislät" pp. 114-138.

Molla Niyazi. "Divan Niyazi," pp. 138-246.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Bähram vä Häptä Mänzär," pp. 247-286.

"Mälikä ziba Čehrä," pp. 287-295.

Issue #11 (1984)

Navayi. "Mäntiquttäyir (davami)," pp. 1-67.

Molla Niyaz Khotäni. "Tot imam täzkirisi," pp. 68-106.

"Divan Zohori," pp. 107-187. [this has been cut out of my copy.]

R. Jari. "Čaghatay ädibiyati niñ shäkillinishi toghrisida qisqičä mulahizä," pp. 188-195.

Ähmät Ziya'i. "Kilassik ädibiyatimizniñ qädimiyliğı vä uniñ čät tillarniñ täsirigä uçrash järyani."
pp. 196-204.

Sabit Äkhmät, Qorban Väli. "Aq sepil qädimqi shähriniñ kesäkliridiki yeziqlar häqqidä däsläpki
mulahizä" pp. 205-211.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Gherip vä Sänäm (khälq dastani)." Batur Ärshidinov (täyyarlighuči) pp. 212-285.

"Adil Padisha (khälq dastani)." pp. 286-329.

"Uyghur khälq qoshaqliridin," pp. 330-354.

Issue #12 (1984)

Navayi. "Mäsnivi vä ruba'ilar," pp. 1-40.

Imir Hosiyin Säburi. "Maqallat," pp. 41-218. [lughät pp. 195-218]

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Näsri Mirza Muhämmät Hosiyin Bäg din Säddi Iskändäri. pp. 219-296.

Khälq eghiz ädibiyatidin:

"Sirlıq Čıraq," pp. 296-311.

"Uyghur khälq qoshaqliridin" pp. 312-338.

Issue #13 (1984)

"Gör Oghli (Khälq dastani)," pp. 1-119.

"Ma'itri simit," pp. 120-149.

Navayi. "Mäntiquttäyir (davami)," pp. 150-228.

Molla Tokhti. "Ärziyät," pp. 229-237.

Salih Damolla Hajim. "Kälkün," pp. 238-245.

"Uyghur khälq qoshaqliridin" pp. 245-262.

Issue #14 (1984)

"Bozkörpäh vä Qarasač Ayim (khälq dastani)," pp. 1-17.

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Näsri Mirza Muhämmäd Hösiyin Bäg din," pp. 18-91.

Äkhmät Yäsävi. "Divan Hikmät," pp. 92-193. [Based on 1299/1879 Turkish edition from the
Osmaniyya Press.]

Abdurehim Nezari. "Čahar Därvish," pp. 194-266.

Muhämmät Sadiq Qäshqiri. "Ghözäl vä Mäsnilär," pp. 267-280.

"Uyghur khälq maqal-tämsilliridin." pp. 281-297.

Issue #15 (1985)

[frontis piece a portrait of Täjälli by Ghazi Ämät.]

"Yüsüp - Zuläykha" pp. 1-71.

Navayi. "Dastan Padisha Iskändär," pp. 72-124.

Mäjlisi. "Säyfulmülük - Bädi'uljamal," pp. 125-193.

"Molla Musa Sayrami She'irliridin Tallanma." pp. 194-227.

Salahi. "Gül vä bulbul," pp. 228-258.

"Uyghur khälq čöčäkliridin" pp. 259-303.

"Näsirdin Äpändi lätipliri," pp. 304-312.

Issue #16 (1985)

"Shirzat vä Gülzat," pp. 1-71. [prepared by Tokhti Abikhan, whose introduction says that this is a Uyghur khälq qissä from a manuscript collection of qissä and hikaya copied in 1771 in

Yäkän. Called Jami'ul Hikayat, and in his possession.]

Navayi. "Dastan Padisha Iskändär," pp. 72-161.

Äkhmät Yäsävi. "Divan Hikmät," pp. 162-274.

Abdurehim Nezari, Noruz Akhun Ziya'i. "Čahar Därvish," pp. 275-324.

Turdi Nazim Gheripi. "Kitabi Gherip," pp. 325-373.

"Säypulmülükniñ hikayisi," pp. 374-409.

Issue #17 (1985)

Abdurehim Nizari, Noruz Akhun Katip Ziya'i. "Čahar Därvish," pp 1-67.

"Uyghur khälq qoshaqliri," pp. 68-69.

"Uyghur khälq maqal-tämsilliri." pp. 70-78.

"Uyghur khälq čöčäkliridin: Täläylik poči" pp. 79-81.

"...: Üç kälimä söz," pp. 82-85.

Navayi. "Dastan Padisha Iskändär," pp. 86-216.

Muhämmäd Gherib Shäh-yari. "Ishtiyaqnamä," pp. 217-312.

Abdurehim Nizari. "Dährunnäjat," pp. 313-352.

Issue #18 (1986)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Ähmädi ghäzälliri" pp. 1-30.

"Täjälli She'irliri" pp. 31-34.

"Abdusämäd She'irliri" pp. 35-37.

A. Nizari, N. Ziya'i. "Čahar Därvish (davami)," pp 38-72.

Jahan kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Abdurahman Jami. "Sälaman vä Äbsal," pp. 73-96.

Mäshhur kilassiklar:

Ärshidin Tatliq, tüzgüči. "Molla Shakir." p. 97.

Abdilhäkim Mäjdum Haji, tüzgüči. "Mävlana Hüsäyin Täjälli," pp. 98-100.

Kilassiklar häqqidä hekayilär:

Zulpiqar. "Yerim äsir yoshurunghan qäbrä (očerker)" pp. 101-108.

Ädibiy Muhakimä:

Mirsultan Osmanov. "Uyghur khälqiniñ kilassik sha'iri Gumnam," pp. 109-120.

Abdushükür Muhämmät'imin. "Ottura äsir jahalitigä oqulghan shikayätinä: Kulliyat Mäsnävi Khärabati toghrisida," pp. 121-128.

Uyghur khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Tahir - Zuhra (dastan)" pp. 129-149.

"Uyghur khälq çöçäkliridin (üç çöçäk)" pp. 150-165.

"Rivayätlär" pp. 166-171.

"Lätipilär," pp. 172-175.

"Aznibaqi 'lap' liri," pp. 176-183.

"Beyt vä qoshaqlar," pp. 184-189.

Yeñi Khävärlär:

Tursun Barat. "Molla Shakirniñ qäbrisi tepildi," pp. 190-197.

"Üçturpanda Molla Shakir tughulghanliqiniñ 179 yilliqi khatiriländi," p. 198.

"Sovet Ittipaqida Bilal Nazim äsärleri Qazaq tilida näshir qilindi," p.199.

"Yaponiyidä Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatiniñ tätqiq qilinish ähvali," pp. 200-201.

"Aldinqi sanlarniñ mundärijisi," pp. 202-212.

Issue #19 (1986)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Muhämmäd Sadiq Qäshqäri. pp. 1-12.

"Ismayil Haji she'irliri" pp. 13-20.

"Aräzi ghäzälliri" pp. 21-42.

A. Nizari, N. Ziya'i. "Čahar Därvish (davami)," pp. 43-71.

Jahan kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Muhämmäd Kharäzmi. "Muhäbbätnamä," pp. 72-84.

Mäshhur kilassiklar:

"Mäshräp - Ulugh insanpärvär sha'ir," pp. 85-92. [no author's name attached to this article!]

M. Shärifzadä. "Äbulhäsän Rudaki," pp. 93-98. [translated from Uzbek by Rozi Muhämmät Jümä]

Ädibiy Muhakimä:

Qasim Arishov. "Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidiki namayändilär," pp. 99-119.

Kilassiklar häqqidä hekayilär:

Tokhtisin Jalalov. "Ikki Sha'iräniġ ädäbiy mirasini izdäp," pp. 120-134.

Uyghur khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Mälikä Mehriliqa (dastan)" pp. 135-159.

"Altun qoġghuraq (čöčäk)," pp. 160-161.

"Hekayät vä lätipilär," pp. 162-166.

"Rivayätlär" pp. 167-172.

"Beyit vä qoshaqlar," pp. 176-180.

"Maqal-tämsillär," pp. 181-183.

"Tepishmaqlar," pp. 184-189.

"Ĉaghatayĉä lughät," pp. 190-233.

Issue #20 (1987)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Muhämmäd Räsul. "Divan shävri," pp. 1-69.

Tokhti Akhunum. "Tuhfätul Ushshaq," pp. 70-91.

Älikhan Mollakhun Oghli. "Aräzi ghäzälliri" pp. 92-112.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Z. M. Babir. "Ghäzällär," pp. 113-135.

Mäshhur kilassiklar:

Abdushükür Muhämmät'imin. "Hapiz Shirazi - shärq she'iritidiki isyankar ustaz," pp. 136-143.

Ädibiy Muhakimä:

V. Zahidov. "Täsävvup häqqidä," pp. 144-164.

Uyghur khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Yalpuzkhan (dastan)" pp. 165-177.

"Lä'li Banum vä Shirinbanum (ĉöĉäk)," pp. 178-194.

"Rivayätlär" pp. 195-202.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 203-208.

"Laplar," pp. 209-213.

"Maqal-tämsillär," pp. 214-215.

"Čaghatayčä lughät," pp. 216-234.

Issue #21 (1987)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Khoja Jahan. "Divani Ärshi," pp. 1-78.

Molla Saleh. "Salehi she'irliridin," 79-107.

Qul'älim. "Töt namä," pp. 108-115.

Molla Davut. "She'irlar." pp. 116-129.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Nizami Äruzi Sämärqäнди. "Nadir Hekayätläär din" pp. 130-147.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Mähämmätturdi Mirzi'äkhmät. "Sha'ir Molla Saleh toghrisida," pp. 148-149.

Mäshhur äsärlär:

Mähämmätnuri Osmanov, Sha'islam Shamuhämmidov. "Shah Kitab," pp. 150-166.

Uyghur khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Äbäydullakhan (dastan)" pp. 167-174.

"Ikki čöčäk," pp. 175-178.

"Rivayätlär" pp. 179-185.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 186-193.

"Laplar," pp. 194-199.

"Ĉaghatayĉä lughät," pp. 200-234.

Issue #22 (1988)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Pazil "Läyli vä Mäjnun," pp. 1-46.

Molla Sabir binni Abdulqadir. "Divani naqis," pp. 47-81.

Molla Häydär. "Miskin she'iliridin," pp. 82-89.

Äsiri, Molla Äläm, Hämdi, Molla Yaqup, Molla Imin. "She'irlar," pp. 90-98.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Ällamä Zämähshäri. "Ätvaquz zähäb tin" pp. 99-111.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Päridä Imin. "Ulugh khälqpärvär sha'ir Molla Pazil," pp. 112-114.

Abdushükür Muhämmät'imin. "Ämir Khusräv Dehlävi," pp. 115-119.

Mäshhur äsärlär:

Mähämmäturdi Mirzi'äkhmät. "Yeñi tepilghan büyük miras," pp. 120-124. [250 ff. manuscript of poetry by Molla Häydär, Molla Saleh, Molla Niyaz. Copied by Molla Imin and Molla Yaqup in 1855 in Khotän. Translations from Persian by Häydär, poems by the three of them, and dastan by Niyaz.]

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Kibriyä Qahharova. "Tekistkä ähmiyät berish keräk," pp. 125-137. [Translated from Sharq Yulduz 1983. Extended critique of 1980 edition of Mashrab published in Tashkent, describing what should have been done to create a critical text.]

Uyghur khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Hävzikhan (khälq dastani)" pp. 138-143.

"Saleh Nävjuvan (çöçäk)," pp. 144-155.

"Äpsanilər," pp. 156-160.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 161-169.

"Maqal-tämsillär," pp. 170-177.

"Čaghatayčä lughät," pp. 178-224.

Issue #23 (1988)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Pazil "Läyli vä Mäjnun (davami)," pp. 5-48.

Molla Sabir binni Abdulqadir. "Divani naqis (davami)," pp. 49-128.

Äkhmätsha Qariqashi. "Mevilər väsfi," pp. 129-134.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Abdurehim Hapiz. "Hapiz Kharäzmi divanidin" pp. 135-160.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

"Sha'ir Äkhmätsha Qariqashi," pp. 161-162.

Abdushükür Muhämmät'imin. "Ulugh mutäpäkkur sha'ir Nizami Gänjäviy," pp. 163-168.

Mäshhur äsärlär:

"Hapiz Kharäzmi vä uniñ divani toghrisida," pp. 169-171.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

I. Säydullayiv. "Muhämmät Sadiq Qäshqäriniñ äkhlaqiy - didaktik mirasi," pp. 172- 175.

Uyghur khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Uyghur khälq čöçäkliridin," pp. 176-179.

"Lätipilär," pp. 180-183.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 184-190.

"Čaghatayčä lughät," pp. 191-220.

Issue #24 (1988)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Räbghuzi. "Qissäsul - Änbiya din (Adäm äläyhissalam qissisi)," pp. 1-28.

Ibni Yüsüp Khotäni. "She'irlar" pp. 28-65.

"Sha'ir Qäländärniñ yeñi tepilghan ghäzälliri," pp. 65-90.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Ämr Kusräv Dehlävi. "Ghäzällär," pp. 91-108.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Abdushükür Muhämmät'imin. "Ulugh mutäpäkkur sha'ir Nasir Khusräv," pp. 109-114.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Abdulla Sulayman. "Nävbäti she'irliriniñ idiyivi mäzmuni häqqidä," pp. 115-122.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"İgärçi (çöçäk)," pp. 123-128.

"Ghayib Nikah (çöçäk)," pp. 129-136.

"Lätipilär (Mätlä'ul - ulum vä Mäjmä'ul - funun din)," pp. 137-148. [translated from Persian.]

"Laplär," pp. 149-152.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar (Elakhun tilivaldi qoshaqliri)," pp. 153-161.

"Maqal-tämsillär," pp. 162-165.

"Čaghatayčä lughät," pp. 166-220.

Issue #25 (1988)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Räbghuzi. "Nuh äläyhissalam qissisi," pp. 1-11. [prepared by Haji Nurhaji]

Räbghuzi. "Ibrahim vä Isma'il äläyhissalam qissisi," pp. 12-38.

Molla Niyaz. "She'irlar" pp. 39-59.

Molla Qurban. "Mäsnävi vä Mukhämmlär," pp. 60-86.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Nizami Gänjavi she'irliridin," pp. 87-98.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Abdushükür Muhämmät'imin. "Sha'ir Khoja Jahan Ärshi vä uniñ she'iriy ijadiyiti häqqidä," pp. 99-115.

Tursun Qahhari. "Säläy Čaqqañ Kim?," pp. 116-119.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

"Sä'di Shirizi," pp. 120-122.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Hünärniñ karamiti (čöčäk)," pp. 123-130.

"Čughul дәlliniñ hiylisi (čöčäk)," pp. 131-134.

"Altun Igär (čöčäk)," pp. 135-140.

"Padishah bilän Malči (čöčäk)," pp. 141-145.

"Yäkkä taz bilän yättä taz (čöčäk)," pp. 146-148.

"Qadimki lätipilär," pp. 149-163. [translated from Uzbek.]

"Mayimkhan qoshaqliri," pp. 164-170.

"Säläy Čaqqañ qoshaqliri," pp. 171-174.

"Laplär," pp. 175-177.

"Čaghatayčä lughät," pp. 178-220.

Issue #26 (1989)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Abduqadir Damollam äsärliridin," pp. 5-35.

Abdukhelil Damollahaji. "She'iriy Mäktublar," pp. 36-56.

Muhämmätrozi Akhunum. "Shähidi She'irliridin," pp. 57-82.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Khoja Názär Ghayib Názär Oghli. "Huväyda she'irliridin," pp. 83-104.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Robert Dankof, Jamis Kelli. "Turkiy tillar divaniy inglizčä tärjimisiniñ müqäddimisi," pp. 105-121.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

A. Jälilop. "Khushhal ghärbiy häqqidä yeñi mälumatlar," pp. 122-124.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Irishkhan," pp. 125-141.

"Aqilliq mälikä (čöčäk)," pp. 142-145.

"Tädbirlik Sotči (čöčäk)," pp. 146-149.

"Uyghur khälq lätipiliri," pp. 150-158.

"Ata - bovilar näsihätliridin," pp. 159-169.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 't'," pp. 170-208.

Issue #27 (1989)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Qisäsul - Änbiya din" pp. 5-27.

"Divan Futuhi din," pp. 28-49.

"Isma'îl Haji She'irliridin," pp. 50-62.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Husäyin Bayqara. "Husäyniy ghäzälliridin," pp. 63-77.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Shirin Qurban. "Abdurakhman Jami," pp 78-81.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Ghulam Kärimov. "Dil'aramu dil'arayu do'asa," pp. 82-96.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Dällä vä Mukhtar (dastan)," pp. 97-123.

"Tälvä Küy'oghul (çöçäk)," pp. 124-128.

"Qunduz vä yultuz (çöçäk)," pp. 129-140.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 141-158.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 159-161.

"Çaghatayçä lughät 't'," pp. 162-206.

Q. Mahmudov, Q. Sadiqov. "Qadimki Türk pütüki - Maytri Simit," pp. 206-208. [Candidates at the Uzbekistan Institute of philological science.]

Issue #28 (1989)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Pärhad vä Shirin," pp. 5-33. [inside back cover has reproductions from the original]

"Isma'îl Haji She'irliridin," pp. 34-79.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Furqät she'irliridin," pp. 80-92.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Shirin Qurban, Mädälikhan. "Pärididin Ättar," pp. 93-96.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Ibrahim Muti'i. "Uyghurlar Islam dinigha yeñi kirgän dävidiki Islam mädrisiliri," pp. 97-112. [Article written after the author's participation in a conference at Harvard organized in memory of Joseph Fletcher (Yosif F. Fileçir), on the theme of "The Introduction of Islam into China," (April 12-16, 1989).

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Dällä vä Mukhtar (dastan)," pp. 113-141.

"Abla Mollam (dastan)," pp. 142-150.

"Gülçehra (çöçäk)," pp. 151-167.

"Ata-bovaylar nāsihätiridin," pp. 168-179.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 'j'," pp. 180-208.

Issue #29 (1989)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Pärhad vä Shirin," pp. 5-72.

Molla Sabir binni Abdulqadir. "Gulzari binish (dastan)," pp. 73-101.

Khoja Jahan Ärshi. "Ghözällär," pp. 102-108.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Gäda'î. "She'irlar," pp. 109-124.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Shükür Yalqin. "Fuzuliy vä uniñ ädäbiy ijadiyiti häqqidä," pp. 125-147.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Shirin Qurban. "Jalalidin Rumi," pp. 148-153.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Yättä čöčäk," pp. 154-160.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 161-170.

"Pändi - näsihätlär," pp. 170-178.

"Säpär qoshaqliri," pp. 179-186.

"Maqal - tämsilliri," p. 187.

"Čaghatayčä lughät ('j' niñ davami)," pp. 188-208.

Issue #30 (1990)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Pärhad vä Shirin," pp. 5-88.

Molla Sabir binni Abdulqadir. "Gulzari binish," pp. 89-118.

"Khushhal Ghärbi she'irliridin," pp. 119-126.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Säyid Ähmäd. "Tä'äshshuqnamä," pp. 127-137. [son of Miranshah, third son of Ämir Tömür Koragan, who lived 1336-1405. The present work written 839 A.H., (1435/36), and consists of 319 pages in the original.]

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Turghun Almas. "Shähnamä dastani häqqidä," pp. 138-159.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

Ablizkhan, Shirin Qurban. "Mutäpäkkur Sha'ir Mirza Abduqadir Bidil," pp. 160-163.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Üč Shahzadä (čöčäk)," pp. 164-172.

"Ibrätlik hekayätläär," pp. 173-184.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 'č'," pp. 185-208.

Issue #31 (1990)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Muhämmätniyaz binni Abdughapur. "Qisäsul - ghärayib tin," pp. 5-31.

Ghäyräti. "Khubmukin (mukhämäs)," pp. 32-35.

"Lutpi ghäzelliridin," pp. 36-61.

"Qädimki Uyghur yeziqidiki she'iriy äsär - Amitayurdyana sutra," pp. 62-88.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Näsimiy ghäzelliridin," pp. 89-104.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Qurban Väli Krorani. "Qutadghu biliktiki Bayat degän nam häqqidä mulahizä," pp. 105-109.

Mäshhur klassiklar:

"Sha'ir Ghäyrati," pp. 110-111.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Hürliqä - Hämrajan (dastan)," pp. 112-133.

"Ikki Khojzadä (čöčäk)," pp. 134-142.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 143-145.

"Muhäbbät qoshaqliri," pp. 146-151.

"Ĉaghatayĉä lughät 'kh'," pp. 152-186.

"Bebli'ogirafiyä," pp. 187-208. [classified index of the first ten years or 30 issues of Bulaq.]

Issue #32 (1990)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Väfa'î, Riza'î, Firaqi, Huzuri, Qärari. "She'irlar," pp. 5-10.

Qäländär. "Divan Qäländär," pp. 11-79.

Abdurehim Nizari. "Hikayati Ghärib (dastan)," pp. 80-95.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Säyfi Särayi äsärliridin," pp. 96-106.

Mäshhur äsärlar:

G. N. Pant. "Baburnamä toghrisida," pp. 107-112. [author at New Dehli museum.]

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Hürliqä - Hämrajan (dastan)," pp. 113-134.

"Mehri bilän Vapa (ĉöĉäk)," pp. 135-150.

"Äpsanilar," pp. 151-155.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 156-169.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 170-175.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 176-180.

"Ĉaghatayĉä lughät 'kh'," pp. 181-208.

Issue #33 (1990)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Abidi Qumuli. "Divani Abid tin," pp. 5-27.

Mävlana Ubäydulla Lutpi. "Gul vä nävrüz," pp. 28-37.

"Mänsur Bakhshi Ghäzälliridin," pp. 38-43.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Hapiz Shirazi she'iritidin," pp. 44-62.

Mäshhur kilassiklar:

Haji Yaqup Yüsüpi. "Mäshhur insiklopidik alim - Shämsiddin Sami," pp. 63-74.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Sänobär (dastan)," pp. 75-93.

"Uyghur khälq čöçäkliridin," pp. 94-110.

"Yiganä jahan bilän yiganä dävrän," pp. 111-125.

"Äpsanilər," pp. 126-140.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 141-149.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 150-158.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 'd'," pp. 159-208.

Issue #34 (1991)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Bähram vä Dil'aram," pp. 5-64.

Imini. "She'irlar," pp. 65-70.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Abdurähman Jami ghäzälliridin," pp. 71-77.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Ibrahim Häqqulov. "Nadanliq - yavuzluq," pp. 78-97.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Sänobär (dastan)," pp. 98-116.

"Känji Küy'oghul (čöčäk)," pp. 117-135.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 136-145.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 146-155.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 'd'," pp. 156-208.

Issue #35 (1991)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Bähram vä Dil'aram," pp. 5-52.

Noruzakhun Katib Ziya'i. "Muhzinul - va'izin," pp. 53-67.

Molla Äli Qushçi. "Baznamä," pp. 68-75.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Shäykhi. "Khärnamä," pp. 76-79.

Mäshhur kilassiklar:

Mähämmättursun Bahavidin. "Shäykhi vä uniñ Khärnamä namliq äsiri toghrisida," pp. 80-82.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Ibrahim Häqqulov. "Ah, sha'ir qismiti," pp. 83-101.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Qizilgül (dastan)," pp. 102-130.

"Mälikä Hösnibanu (çöçäk)," pp. 131-135.

"Beliqçi bovary bilän su pärisi (çöçäk)," pp. 136-141.

"Uyghur khälq lätipiliri," pp. 142-146.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 147-152.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 153-157.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 'r'," pp. 157-208.

Issue #36 (1991)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Bähram vä Dil'aram," pp. 5-41.

Qul'älim Ami Zä'if. "She'irlar," pp. 42-65.

Noruzakhun Katib Ziya'i. "Muhzinul - va'izin," pp. 66-83.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Jalalidin Rumi she'irlidin," pp. 83-92.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Äziz Äli. "Qosh täkhällusluq khushnva bulbul," pp. 93-97.

Mäshhur äsärlär:

Khämit Tömür. "Dunyavi mäshhur äsär - Babur Namä," pp. 98-120.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Aq'ulambädikhan (dastan)," pp. 121-134.

"Shahzadä Nurdiyar (čöčäk)," pp. 135-148.

"Ajayib sät (čöčäk)," pp. 149-153.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 154-157.

"Lätipilär," pp. 158-164.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 165-172.

"Ĉaghatayĉä lughät 'r'," pp. 173-208.

Issue #37 (1991)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Imin Tursun. "Näva'iniñ 550 yilliqi," pp. 6-13.

Ömür Baqi Yärkändi. "Läyli vä Mäjnun," pp. 14-29.

Durbek. "Yüsüp vä Ziläykha," pp. 30-49.

"Qäländärniñ yeñi tepilghan she'irliri," pp. 50-58.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Khojändi. "Lätifätnamä," pp. 59-67.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Dilbär Roziyiva. "Abdurehim Nizariniñ hayati vä ijadiy pa'aliyiti häqqidä," pp. 68-86.

Mäshhur äsärlär:

Mähämmättursun Bahavidin. "Khojändi vä uniñ Lätifätnamä si toghrisida," pp. 87-88.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Qara qoshunluqlar qoshiqi," pp. 89-99.

"Börä qiz (ĉöĉäk)," pp. 100-106.

"Hekimzadä bilän shahzadä (čöčäk)," pp. 107-109.

"Yäkčäshmä bilän yantaqči (čöčäk)," pp. 110-114.

"Molla Mishriq (čöčäk)," pp. 115-116.

"Altun müngüzlük qočqar (čöčäk)," pp. 117-119.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 120-131.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 132-140.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 141-150.

"Čaghatayčä lughät 'z'," pp. 151-208.

Issue #38 (1992)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Shähnamä 'ı türkiy din," pp. 5-27.

"Nizari mukhämmäsliri," pp. 27-81.

Mäjlisi. "Shäyful - mälik vä bädi'ul - jämal," pp. 82-106.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"İbni Sina she'irliridin," pp. 107-116.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Dilbär Roziyeva. "Abdurehim Nizariniñ hayati vä ijadiy pa'aliyiti toghrisidä," pp. 117-128.

Mäshhur kilassiklar:

Qutluq Qadir. "Ulugh mutäpäkkur alim Näsriiddin Äl-Tusi," pp. 129-130.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Shahzadä Bähram vä Mälikä Dilriz (dastan)," pp. 131-142.

"Shah Adilkhan (čöčäk)," pp. 143-146.

"Sänävbär gülgä nemä qildi, gül sänävbärgä nemä qildi (čöčäk)," pp. 147-164.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 165-170.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 171-174.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 175-177.

"Čaghatayčä lughät," pp. 178-207.

"Näva'î tughulghanliqiniñ 550 yilliqi khatirländi," p. 208.

Issue #39 (1992)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Shähnamä'î türkiy din," pp. 5-40.

Turdush Akhun Ghäribi. "She'irlar," pp. 41-56.

Mäjlisi. "Shäyful - mälik vä bädi'ul - jämäl," pp. 57-76.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

"Yüsüp Ämiri she'irliridin," pp. 77-81.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Mämtimin Yüsüp. "Uyghur klassik ädäbiyatidin bir tamčä," pp. 82-90.

Muhämmätjan Häkimov. "Älishir Näva'ı äsärlerini köçürgän khättatlar," pp. 91-109.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Gülshah - väräqä (dastan)," pp. 110-145.

"Shahzadä Bähram vä Mälikä Dilriz (dastan)," pp. 146-158.

"Tul Khotunniñ oghli (çöçäk)," pp. 159-169.

"Otunçiniñ jasariti (çöçäk)," pp. 180-185.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 186-194.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 195-199.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 200-206.

Mehrigül Tursun. "Shinjañ UAR luq Uyghur klassik ädäbiyati tätqiqat jäm'iyiti quruldi," p. 207

Dilshad Sultan, trans. "Iranda Firdävsini khatrläp khälq'a muhakimäyighini ötküzüldi," p. 208.

Issue #40 (1992)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Mulla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Säddi Iskändäriy," pp. 5-61.

Molla Yunus. "Muhäbbätnamä," pp. 62-110.

"Zuhuri she'irliridin," pp. 111-131.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Biruni, Ghäzzali. "Hekayätlär," pp. 132-140.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Abdurehim Sabit. "Yüsüp Khas Hajip qäbrigahi toghrisidiki tarikhiy hüjjätlär," pp. 141-144.

Muhämmätjan Häkimov. "Älishir Näva'ı äsärlirini köçürgän khättatlar," pp. 145-157.

Mäshhur Klassiklar:

Tursun Hushur. Muhämmäd Mirza Häydär Koragan vä unıñ äsärliri toghrisida," pp. 158-165.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Khemirkhan (çöçäk)," pp. 159-169.

"Sänji sämi tash (çöçäk)," pp. 170-179.

"Lätipilär," pp. 179-183.

"Rivayätlär," pp. 184-191.

"Ibrätlik hekayätlär," pp. 192-203.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 204-208.

Issue #41 (1992)

Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Molla Sidiq Yärkändi. "Säddi Iskändäriy," pp. 5-70.

Molla Yunus. "Muhäbbätnamä," pp. 71-99.

"Mäzhäri she'irliridin," pp. 100-107.

Noruzakhun Katib Ziya'ı. "Müshük bilän çashqan," pp. 108-111.

Shärq kilassik ädäbiyatidin:

Biruni, Ghäzzali. "Hekayätlär," pp. 132-140.

Ädäbiy Muhakimä:

Nizamul - Mulk. "Siyasätnamä din," pp. 112-119.

Ämir Umärkhan. "Divani Ämiri din," pp. 120-142.

Ädäbiy muhakimä:

Qadir Äkbär. "Mädäniy miraslar vä milliy än'änilärgä varisliq qilish mäsilisi toghrisida," pp. 143-149.

Jappar Ämiät. "Näva'í öz äsäriliridä qančä söz ishlätgän," pp. 150-151.

Abdushükür Muhämmätimin. "Klassik ädäbiyatta Khotän täsviri," pp. 152-161.

Khälq eghiz ädäbiyatidin:

"Mälikä zärnigar (dastan)," pp. 162-181.

"Padiči bilän padishah (čöčäk)," p. 182.

"Niyiti yamanniñ qazini töshük (čöčäk)," pp. 183-184.

"Kishini qästligän özini qästläptu (čöčäk)," pp. 185-187.

"Aldamčiniñ aqiviti (čöčäk)," pp. 188-189.

"Mähmud Qäshqäriy häqqidä rivayätlär," pp. 190-198.

"Beyit - qoshaqlar," pp. 199-208.